

Distribution of Water Quality Concerning Sea Surface Temperature and Dissolved Oxygen Using Landsat 8 Satellite Imagery on the Tuban Coast, East Java

Siti Zainab¹, Novie Handajani¹, Hendrata Wibisana¹, Primasari Cahya Wardhani^{1*}

¹ Civil Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, UPN Veteran East Java, Surabaya, Indonesia

Abstract:- The coast of Tuban is a fairly dynamic area where the lives of fishers depend on fishing. Changes in the eco system in Tuban's coastal area significantly affect fishing activities. One of the parameters that can be observed is the distribution of oxygen content and sea surface temperature of the water bodies on the coast. Sea surface temperature and dissolved oxygen have a vital role as a determinant of water quality and are crucial factors for the life of organisms in the ocean.

This study aims to analyze the distribution of nutrients in sea surface temperature and dissolved oxygen with Landsat 8 Satellite Imagery, a Case Study on the coast of Tuban, using a computer unit and Seadas 4.7.3 software.

Identifying the Tuban coastal area is to get the distribution of sea surface temperature (SST) in the range of 27.717136904597°C to 40.287807002664°C, while dissolved oxygen has a range from 4.670533359051 mg/L to 4.820914387703 mg/L. Dissolved Oxygen Algorithm Model $y = 0.0734\ln(x) + 4.8917$ with $R^2 = 0.2677$, Sea surface temperature (SST) Algorithm Model $y = 4.8634\ln(x) + 44.941$ with $R^2 = 0.2872$.

The correlation between sea surface temperature (SST) and dissolved oxygen from Landsat 8 satellite imagery is a linear model Y (Dissolved Oxygen) = 91.246 X (Sea Surface Temperature) - 399.14.

Keywords:- sea surface temperature; dissolved oxygen; Landsat 8 image; Tuban Coastal Area.

I. INTRODUCTION

In general, East Java's coastal marine area can be grouped into the north coast, south coast, and east coast. Tuban Regency is one of the northern coastal areas. The northern coast of East Java is a low-lying area whose height is almost the same as sea level. Coastal areas are often used for various activities such as residential areas, aquaculture, tourism, et cetera. The utilization of coastal areas requires good management because environmental conditions are influenced by many factors such as wind, sea currents, tides, abrasion, sedimentation, etc. [1][2][3]

The coast of Tuban is a fairly dynamic area where the lives of fishers depend on fishing activities. Changes in the ecosystem in Tuban's coastal area significantly affect fishing activities. One of the parameters that can be observed is the distribution of oxygen content and sea surface temperature from water bodies on the coast [4][1].

Sea surface temperature and dissolved oxygen have a vital role as a determinant of water quality and are crucial factors for the life of organisms in the ocean [5], because these two variables indicate the presence of nutrients and the presence of chlorophyll as food for marine biota.

This study aims to analyze the distribution of nutrients in sea surface temperature and dissolved oxygen with Landsat 8 Satellite Imagery Case Study on the coast of Tuban, using a computer unit and Seadas 4.7.3 software [6][7].

This study uses a computer unit, Seadas 5.7.3 software, and secondary data from Landsat 8 satellite imagery launched on February 11, 2013. This earth monitoring satellite has two sensors, namely Operational Land Imager (OLI) and Thermal Infrared Sensors (TIRS). These two sensors provide a spatial resolution of 30 meters (visible, NIR, SWIR), 100 meters (thermal), and 15 meters (panchromatic). Landsat 8 is more suitable to be called a satellite with a mission to continue Landsat 7 than to be called a new satellite with new specifications. This can be seen from its characteristics, similar to Landsat 7 in terms of resolution (spatial, temporal, and spectral), correction method, flight altitude, and the sensors' characteristics. However, several additions become the improvement points of Landsat 7, such as the number of channels, the lowest electromagnetic wave spectrum range that the sensor can capture, and the bit value (Digital Number value range) of each image pixel. Landsat 8 satellite has Onboard Operational Land Imager (OLI) and Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) sensors with 11 channels [8].

Among these channels, nine channels (channels 1-9) are on OLI, and two others (Channels 10 and 11) are on TIRS. Most of the channels have specifications similar to Landsat 7. In the interests of marine and fisheries management, efficient and effective sources of data and information are supported by cheap and fast data types [6][9][10]. Some of the issues to be aware of include:

- How does this study identify areas to get the distribution of sea surface temperature (SST) throughout and dissolved oxygen in the entire coastal area of Tuban?
- How does this study comprehend the estimation of sea surface temperature (SST) and dissolved oxygen in the coastal area of Tuban?
- How is the correlation between sea surface temperature (SST) and dissolved oxygen from Landsat 8 satellite imagery throughout the coastal area of Tuban?

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Landsat 8 satellite imagery data was taken from the website <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/> with the election time being June 2022 according to the date of sampling Sea Surface Temperature in the field [11][12].

The variable studied was sea surface temperature/SST in the coastal area of Tuban, Tuban Regency. The next step is image cropping, to reduce the image display area according to the coordinates of the desired area. This aims to make the file size smaller, making the processing process faster. For data processing purposes, observations are made by creating an Area of interest (AOI) by determining the coordinates. The coordinates of the research location are 112.245 East Longitude to 112.973 West Longitude and -6.764 North Latitude to -7.203 South Latitude. The average sea surface temperature data distribution was extracted from Landsat 8 satellite imagery.

• Data processing stage

- Opening the downloaded image data using the SeaDAS application. Cropping, this process is done so that the position of the research area looks clearer and focuses on that area only.
- Reprojecting the cropped image. Carrying out this reprojection process aims to make the map position based on the actual coordinates on the earth. The following is an image display after the reprojection process.
- Take digital number data by pinning the part under study. In the process of giving this pin, the longitude and latitude position for each period must be the same so that 20 points can be compared as material for calculations.
- Adjusting SeaDAS image data with Microsoft Excel tables 1 and 2. High accuracy is required in transferring data from SeaDAS to Ms.Excel due to several formats that need adjustment and different data readings between the two. Processing the first 20 data of each wave with scatter to get a mathematical equation with the best degree of determination/ R^2 .

- Entering the equation obtained by clicking on the math band to get a thematic map image, namely a map of the distribution of dissolved oxygen and sea surface temperature presented in Figures 2, 3, and

III. RESULTS

The survey data below are the coordinates and measurements of dissolved oxygen and sea surface temperature.

Fig. 1: Tuban coastal area research location map

The satellite image data used in this study is Landsat 8 image taken from web <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/> web page. Filename:
 LC08_L1TP_118065_20220416_20220420_02_T1_B2,
 LC08_L1TP_118065_20220416_20220420_02_T1_B3,
 LC08_L1TP_118065_20220416_20220420_02_T1_B4
 The image data is Level 2 image data downloaded for June 2022 as shown in Figure 1.

Point	Lon	Lat	SST/°C	Dissolved Oxygen/mg/L
1	112,342761	-6,867808	35,4	4,78
2	112,343069	-6,866683	36,3	4,79
3	112,345591	-6,866280	32,6	4,79
4	112,346547	-6,865337	31,5	4,78
5	112,348434	-6,865004	29,3	4,77
6	112,349364	-6,864002	28,2	4,75
7	112,351177	-6,862529	29,1	4,74
8	112,353707	-6,861343	28,8	4,61
9	112,355353	-6,860792	24,5	4,62
10	112,356747	-6,860072	19,2	4,75
11	112,358198	-6,859461	23,7	4,62
12	112,356620	-6,859603	28,6	4,63
13	112,353366	-6,860206	35,4	4,78
14	112,350107	-6,861107	36,2	4,64
15	112,347874	-6,862097	38,2	4,65
16	112,345896	-6,863217	38,9	4,78
17	112,343811	-6,864691	39,6	4,79
18	112,342892	-6,865708	39,1	4,79
19	112342080	-6,867094	40,0	4,80
20	112,8341721	-6,869154	40,1	4,80

Table 1: SST and Dissolved Oxygen data and coordinate data

Source: taken from field measurement

Dissolved Oxygen Data Processing with Reflectance Band 2

Below is a table of reflectance band 2 for dissolved oxygen, such as the following data,

Point	Digital Number	Reflectance Band 2	Digital Number	Reflectance Band 3	Digital Number	Reflectance Band 4
1	21327	0,32654	20245	0,30490	19974	0,29948
2	14967	0,19934	13449	0,16898	12362	0,14724
3	11386	0,12772	10040	0,10080	8387	0,06774
4	10848	0,11696	9691	0,09382	8021	0,06042
5	12951	0,15902	9398	0,08796	7742	0,05484
6	10560	0,11112	9066	0,08132	7494	0,04988
7	10514	0,11028	8992	0,07984	7399	0,04798
8	10627	0,11254	9117	0,08234	7526	0,05052
9	11830	0,1366	10313	0,10626	9243	0,08486
10	10855	0,1171	9003	0,08006	7518	0,05036
11	11015	0,1203	9327	0,08654	7830	0,0566
12	10492	0,10984	8842	0,07684	7368	0,04736
13	10713	0,11426	9166	0,08332	7635	0,0527
14	10390	0,1078	8822	0,07644	7347	0,04694
15	10677	0,11354	9130	0,08260	7607	0,05214
16	11356	0,12712	9967	0,09934	8428	0,06856
17	11728	0,13456	10221	0,10442	8729	0,07458
18	19492	0,28984	19218	0,28436	19057	0,28114
19	21262	0,32524	21483	0,32966	21494	0,32988
20	16421	0,22842	17720	0,25440	14467	0,18934

Table 2: Data Value of Digital Number and Reflectance Band2, Band3, Band4

Source: taken from field measurement

SeaDAS software version 7.5.3 provides a digital number to change the digital number into a reflectance in band 2, band 3, and band 4 using the following formula:

$$\text{Reflectance band } x = \text{Digital Number} * 0.000002 - 0.1$$

Below is presented a scatter diagram to determine the best algorithm model.

No	Algorithm	Mathematical model Dissolved Oxygen	R ²	Mathematical model SST	R ²
BAND_2	Linear	$y = 0,4936x + 4,6448$	0,1473	$y = 28,182x + 26,553$	0,0905
	Exponent	$y = 4,6447e^{0,1047x}$	0,1466	$y = 26,286e^{0,9488x}$	0,083
	Logarithmic	$y = 0,1012\ln(x) + 4,9183$	0,1708	$y = 5,0686\ln(x) + 40,737$	0,0808
	Power	$y = 4,9223x^{0,0215}$	0,1698	$y = 42,383x^{0,1707}$	0,0742
BAND_3	Linear	$y = 0,4089x + 4,6785$	0,2330	$y = 30,001x + 27,283$	0,1108
	Exponent	$y = 4,6782e^{0,0866x}$	0,2314	$y = 26,943e^{1,0089x}$	0,1014
	Logarithmic	$y = 0,0734\ln(x) + 4,8917$	0,2677	$y = 4,8601\ln(x) + 41,782$	0,1138
	Power	$y = 4,8943x^{0,0156}$	0,2659	$y = 43,942x^{0,1641}$	0,105
BAND_4	Linear	$y = 0,3558x + 4,6954$	0,2080	$y = 33,403x + 29,207$	0,2558
	Exponent	$y = 4,6949e^{0,0754x}$	0,2066	$y = 28,779e^{1,044x}$	0,2268
	Logarithmic	$y = 0,0533\ln(x) + 4,8669$	0,2474	$y = 4,8634\ln(x) + 44,941$	0,2872
	Power	$y = 4,8685x^{0,0113}$	0,2457	$y = 47,058x^{0,152}$	0,2546

Table 3: Recapitulation of bands 2, 3, and band 4 is the most optimal

Source: take from field measurement

IV. DISCUSSION

Table 3 Recapitulation of the three bands, it is shown that for dissolved oxygen the best interest/response is in band 3 logarithmic model $y = 0.0734\ln(x) + 4.8917$ with $R^2 = 0.2677$ while sea surface temperature has the best response in band_4 logarithmic model $y = 4.8634\ln(x) + 44.941$ with $R^2 = 0.2872$. Below is a histogram of each band.

Fig. 2 Histogram of the Band 2 reflectance of a Landsat 8 satellite image

Fig. 3: Histogram of the Band 3 reflectance of a Landsat 8 satellite image

Fig. 4: Histogram of the Band 4 reflectance of a Landsat 8 satellite image

The following is a thematic map of Dissolved Oxygen in band 3 logarithmic model $y = 0.0734\ln(x) + 4.8917$. Dissolved oxygen ranges between 4.670533359051 mg/L to 4.820914387703 mg/L in the coastal area of Tuban. The thematic map below shows that the redder the dissolved oxygen is getting lower while the bluer the dissolved oxygen is getting higher. In the Decree of the Minister of the Environment, the standard of seawater quality for marine biota is greater than five, so the dissolved oxygen level in the coastal area of Tuban is less suitable for the life of marine biota.

Fig. 5: Dissolved Oxygen Band_3 distribution map Landsat 8 satellite image

The following is a thematic map of the best sea surface temperature on band_4 logarithmic model $y = 4.8634\ln(x) + 44.941$ with its histogram. The picture shows that the more toward the blue, the lower the sea surface temperature, while the more it leads toward the brown, the sea surface temperature is getting higher.

Fig. 6: Distribution map of Sea Surface Temperature Band_4 satellite imagery Landsat 8

Thematic map Overlay of Sea Surface Temperature Distribution to Dissolved Oxygen Landsat 8 satellite imagery model Logarithmic algorithm:
 Y (Dissolved Oxygen) = 91.246 X (Sea Surface Temperature) - 399.14

Fig. 7 Thematic Map Overlay Sea Surface Temperature Distribution Band_4 Landsat 8 satellite image

V. CONCLUSION

Identifying the Tuban coastal area is to obtain the distribution of sea surface temperature (SST) in the range of 27,717136904597°C to 40,287807002664°C, while dissolved oxygen has a range from 4.670533359051 mg/L to 4.820914387703 mg/L in the coastal area of Tuban. In the Decree of the Minister of Environment, the standard of seawater quality for marine biota is greater than five. At the same time, the dissolved oxygen level in the coastal area of Tuban is 4.820914387703 mg/L < 5, so the coastal area of Tuban is less suitable for the life of marine life. The correlation between sea surface temperature (SST) and dissolved oxygen from Landsat 8 satellite imagery is a logarithmic algorithm model Y (Dissolved Oxygen) = 91.246 X (Sea Surface Temperature) - 399.14.

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